

Selection Process: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1

Building digital skills training and lesson development capacity in the Netherlands NES domain (DC4NES) Project | 2026

Overview

Call 1 (March – May 2026) uses an institutional nomination process. This document describes the process.

Timeline

- Call opens: 4 March – 29 May 2026
- Information session(s): March – April 2026
- Review and selection of applications: June 2026
- Applicants notified: June 2026
- Training: October 2026, on location in the Netherlands/ online

Process

1. The eligibility and selection criteria were informed by a survey distributed to the research community in late 2025. Survey results are published on Zenodo and on the 4TU.ResearchData Collaborations > Digital Capacity for NES page.
2. The project team (Carpentries Coordinators Network NL) developed the eligibility and selection criteria for Call 1 based on the survey results.
3. A list of eligible institutions was developed as follows: institutes belonging to NES were identified by making a list based on membership with TDCC-NES (found here: [TDCC-NES Governance - TDCC.nl](#)) and a list of DCCs in the Netherlands (found here: [DCC - LCRDM.nl](#)), further supplemented by a list of institutes eligible for NWO funding. Institutes outside the NES domain (e.g., UMCs) were excluded.
4. Eligible institutions will receive a formal invitation to nominate candidates, including a link to the application form and the eligibility criteria document.
5. Each institution submits a nomination form for their candidate(s).
6. The project team checks all nominations against the eligibility criteria.
7. Nominations that do not meet the eligibility criteria are returned to the institution with a brief explanation. Institutions may resubmit before the deadline.
8. Each eligible institution may nominate up to two candidates; given the number of eligible institutions, the maximum number of nominations is estimated at 35 seats.
9. All nominations that meet eligibility criteria are accepted. Selection criteria have not been developed for Call 1, as oversubscription is not anticipated. Any unused seats will roll over to Call 2.
10. Accepted candidates are notified and receive practical information about the training.

Related documents

You can find all related documents in the Digital Capacity for NES community on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dc4nes>

- Eligibility Criteria: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1
- Selection Criteria: Carpentries Instructor Training Seats — Call 1